

Assessment of Sex-For-Grade on Attitude of Students in Bayelsa Sate College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Sex-for-Grade has been seen as a corrupt practice bedeviling the nation's educational system. This study was purposed to assess sex-for-grade on the attitude of students in Bayelsa Sstate College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive research design upon a sample of 310 students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Nigeria. The study used multi-stage sampling techniques to select sample for the study. A self-designed instrument was used to elicit data from respondents. The study used pie-chart, mean and standard deviation to present and analyze data. The null hypothesis was tested at .05 level of significance. Results showed that 49% of students had experienced sexual harassment in higher institutions in one form or the other. Another finding was that verbal sexual harassment was 76% extent of occurrence which makes it most frequently occurring form of sex-for-grade in higher institutions. The study discovered that *p value* of .050 for a 2-tailed test was greater than the chosen alpha of .05. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perception toward sex-for-grade was gender unbiased. The study concludes that sex-for-grade is a frequently increasing act in tertiary institutions and the attitudes and perception of students towards sex-for-grade is non-directional. Among other recommendations, the study recommends that government should through the relevant agencies such as Ministry of Education, Accreditation Boards/Councils and Tertiary Institutions to ensure the establishment of effective guidance and counselling centers in all tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Keyword: sex-for-grade, sexual harassment, attitude, perception, and students.

Introduction

Academic success is a fundamental goal for all tertiary institutions in Nigeria. However, the educational institutions in Nigeria have been subjected to criticism as people began to doubt the quality of graduates and their certificates upon graduation. It is no longer news for the uncontrollable occurrences of malpractice ranging from resorting of lecturers or examination officers to cheating in examination halls with different technological gazettes, most worrisomely in this era of Artificial Intelligence. As this episode is yet to be abated, malpractice has taken another amoebic form known as sex-for-grade.

Sex-for-grade is an act whereby members of the academia (students, teaching and non-teaching staff) exchange favours for good grades. In this study sex-for-grade is interchangeably used with sexual harassment. Sexual harassment is an unwelcome sexual advance, request for sexual favours either verbal or physical conduct of sexual nature (Aluede, 2000). Sex-for-grade is a silent disease that is seriously eroding academic excellence in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It is often perceived as a behaviour that is unwelcome (the recipient does not want it) unsolicited (recipient did not ask for it) and repeated. Aluede (2000) opined that the behaviour could be considered sexual harassment when: (i) Submission to such act is explicitly or implicitly a term or condition for an individual's employment or participating in educational programs. (ii) Submission to, or rejection of such conduct by an individual is used as a basis for employment or academic decisions affecting the individual. (iii) When such conduct has the purpose or effect of unreasonably interfering with an employee's work performance or student's academic performance, creating an intimidating hostile or offensive working or learning environment.

For udechukwu et al. (2020), sexual harassment is an unsolicited and unreciprocated sexual behaviour from a person to elicit unwanted sexual relations from another person. The definition identifies the various behaviours that may constitute sexual harassment in a work environment. The first two provisions deal with unequal power relations between the employer/supervisor and employee/subordinate. An employer or a supervisor demands sexual gratification from the employee or subordinate in return for job benefits. In the academic environment, a parallel situation could be argued to arise when faculty members proposed to female students for sexual favours in return for favourable examination results.

The third provision refers to the existence of hostile work environment where offending behaviour interferes with satisfactory work performance of an employee. Tertiary institutions in Nigeria have been bedeviled with obscene dressing, secrete cult activities and drug abuse to mention a few. Most female students almost go naked display their navels and boobs and wearing what are just ample cleavages on display depicting size and shape of the private parts with minis that barely cover their bottom (Queensoap, 2024).

Queensoap (2024) further reveals that respondents' perception regarding social factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria was very high. The previous study affirms a population mean and standard deviation of 4.13 ± 1.14 with a mean percentage of 83%. The social factors investigated and adjudged high were mode of dressing (4.42 ± 1.16 with 88%); visiting of lecturers' offices at odd hours ($4.62 \pm .92$ with 92%); cultural influence (3.33 ± 1.23 with 67%); social media (3.81 ± 1.24 with 78%) and lecturers' unguided relationship with students (4.53 ± 1.01 with 91%). These actual values implies that there are social factors that can promote sex-for-grade in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The previous study concludes that both students and lecturers affirm similarly the observed socio-political factors as influencers of sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria (Queensoap, 2024). It is obvious that students agreeing that their dressing pattern can promote sex-for-grade, yet they still dress almost naked on campus and in classrooms. What should be their attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade? Attitude is an individual's predisposition to respond in a characteristic's way to some features of the social environment (Ogbebor & Egbule, 2006). According to Stamovlasis et al. (2023), the most prevailing types of sexually harassing behaviors, which were experienced mainly by women students, included offensive sexual comments/jokes/stories, inappropriate comments about one's body/appearance/sex life, as well as obscene ways of staring, obscene gestures, and/or exposure of body parts causing embarrassment.

In a similar study, the authors suggest that majority (81%) of the participants responded that sexual harassment is related to all unwelcome sexual behaviour, 72% of the participants feel most afraid of sexual harassment during night, and 83% of the participants responded that the most probable place for sexual harassment is public transport and 91% of the participants believed that the incidences of the sexual harassment have increased in the last 10 years (Pandey, et al., 2021). The study posited that the definition of sexual harassment can differ according to individual's perception. To understand how people perceive and define sexual harassment is crucial for explaining and understanding how they react to sexual harassment and why they often do not stand up against sexual harassment (Pandey, et al., 2021). This denotes that students' attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade is required to ascertain the occurrences of sex-for-grade in tertiary institutions. It is also possible to establish the peculiarity of students' attitudes and perceptions, that is, how they react to sex-for-grade in a particular tertiary institution to corroborate with existing studies. This becomes necessary due to the trend at which sex-for-grade had spread in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

The increasing rate of sex-for-grade in Nigerian institutions of higher learning is a problem of considerable magnitude. It is an ethical and a human right issue that has implications not only for the quality and integrity of the educational system, but also for the physical, mental and social wellbeing of its victims. It is an issue that should be taken seriously due to the gravity of the physical, psychological, academic, social and legal implications it may portends (Oweifabo & Queensoap, 2024). According to Queensoap (2024), sex-for-grade has become a hydra headed problem that has attracted concern from stakeholders of educational institutions especially the higher institutions in the country. This implies that sex-for-grade is the new enemy of academic prowess which is capable in lowering standard of education if not addressed. In another study, it was observed that sex-for-grade as a social and academic problem is not limited to Nigeria. It is a global matter that needs urgent attention (Smart, 2023).

Abdussalam (2020) posited that year after year there have been allegations of sexual harassment by lecturers in these institutions, especially in Federal Universities. Abdussalam further explained that students in these universities usually resort to social media to complain about their experiences of sexual harassment by their lecturers and when asked to report the incidences, they say that the school does not do anything, saying that those lecturers have families to feed and cater for and losing their job could be disastrous for them.

Again, another source stated that in recent times stories have been flying around concerning the situation of things in Nigerian universities especially cases of sexual harassment of females students by male lecturers. The society as well, has been condemning very seriously male lecturers who harass female students or even demand sex to enable these to pass their courses (Omonigho, 2019). This trend is amazing and disturbing in an environment that is often believed to be a center of excellence, be a molding and filtering ground for building virile leaders and intellectuals that will mount the stage of leadership of the country tomorrow. Consequently, How do students react to the act of sex-for-grade? How do they perceive the act of sex-for-grade?, are questions that beg for answers. This study was to assess the attitude and perception of students toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Ogbia-Town.

Objectives of Study

The purpose of this study was to assess sex-for-grade on attitude of students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study was to:

1. Determine rate of sex-for-grade occurrence in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi
2. Assess students' attitudes towards sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi.
3. Determine students' perception of sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi.

Research Questions

The researcher posed the following research questions to guide the study:

1. To what extent do sex-for-grade occur in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?
2. What are the attitudes of students toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?
3. How do students perceive sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Hypothesis

The study tested the following null hypothesis at .05 error of probability:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perceptions toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi

Methodology

This current study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was suitable for the study because it enabled the researcher to collect, summarize and describe variables at their natural setting. This involves the use of a study instrument to obtain data without manipulating the independent variables (students' attitude and perceptions). The study's population consisted of students of Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. The students' population was 1373 which excludes year one students who had not written examinations at the time of the conduct of the study. A sample size of 310 was determined by using Taro Yamen's formula. The researchers employed stratified random sampling technique and simple random sampling technique. A self-designed research instrument was used to obtain data. The instrument was validated using face and content validity methods. The study instrument was determined reliable through Cronbach Alpha which gave a reliability coefficient of .78 which was high enough to consider the instrument reliable. Charts, mean and standard deviations were used for the analysis of data while independent t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at .05 alpha level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Distribution of Respondents' Sexual Harassment Experiences

A look at figure 1 shows that 49% of the respondents had experienced sexual harassment in one form or the other, 47% of the respondents had not experienced sexual harassment while on 4% of the respondents indicated undecided. This denotes that majority of students in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi had experienced sexual harassment in one form or the other.

Figure 1: A Pie Chart Showing Response Level of Students on Sex-for-Grade Experiences in BYCOHTECH

Research Question 1

To what extent do sex-for-grade occur in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for Extent of Sex-for-Grade Occurrences in BYCOHTECH

Statements	N	Mean	Std	Mean %	Criterion mean	Decision
Physical sexual harassment	310	2.91	1.07	73	2.5	Accepted
Verbal sexual harassment	310	3.05	.97	76		Accepted
Non-verbal sexual harassment	310	2.72	.93	68		Accepted
Quid pro quo sexual harassment	310	2.95	.79	74		Accepted
Grand mean/std	310	2.91	.94	73		Accepted

Source: Field work

Table 1 shows extent of sex-for-grade experiences in BYCOHTECH. It was observed that physical sexual harassment (unwanted touch, unwanted kissing) has a mean and standard deviation of 2.91 ± 1.07 with mean percentage of 73 extent of occurrence. For verbal sexual harassment (use of threatening words) has a mean/standard deviation of $3.05 \pm .97$ with mean percentage of 76 extent of occurrence while non-verbal sexual harassment (writing of love letters, text messages, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger & Telegram) has a mean/standard deviation of $2.72 \pm .93$ with mean percentage of 68. For the quid pro quo sexual harassment, students' response mean/standard deviation was $2.95 \pm .79$ with mean percentage of 74 extent of occurrence. These sample mean values suggest that there was high extent of sex-for-grade occurrence in BYCOHTECH. Table 1 revealed a population mean of $2.91 \pm .94$ with mean percentage of 73 rate of sex-for-grade occurrences. Since, calculated mean was greater than the critical mean (2.5), the rate of sex-for-grade occurrence off and in school was high in BYCOHTECH.

Research Question 2

What are the attitudes of students toward sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for students' attitude toward sex-for-grade

Statements	N	Mean	Std	Mean %	Criterion mean	Decision
Sex-for-grade is part of fun in higher institutions	310	3.25	1.47	65	3.0	Accepted
Sex-for-grade should not be encouraged	310	3.44	1.50	69		Accepted
Sex-for-grade should not be seen as a crime when students involve themselves	310	3.50	1.31	70		Accepted
Sex-for-grade helps promote students' academic success	310	2.56	1.32	51		Rejected
Sex-for-grade is a corrupt practice done by lecturers	310	4.38	.78	88		Accepted
Lecturers involved in sex-for-grade should be punished	310	4.34	1.00	87		Accepted
Grand mean/std	310	3.58	1.23	72	Accepted	

Source: field work

Table 2 shows mean/standard deviation of students' attitudes towards sex-for-grade as 3.23 ± 1.47 , 3.50 ± 1.31 , $4.38 \pm .78$, and 4.34 ± 1.00 . These results were greater than the criterion mean of 3.0 hence it indicates that respondents accepted that sex-for-grade was part of fun, it should be encouraged, it should not be seen as a crime, it is usually perpetrated by lecturers and thus such lecturers should be punished in higher institutions however respondents reject the predisposition to accept that sex-for-grade helps to promote students' academic success because respondents' mean/standard deviation was 2.56 ± 1.32 which was less than the criterion mean of 3.0. It was also observed that the grand mean/standard deviation was 3.58 ± 1.23 with a mean percentage of 72% indicating a high level of predisposition towards sex-for-grade.

Research Question 3

How do students' perceived sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi?

Table 3: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for Students' Perception toward Sex-for-grade

Statements	N	Mean	Std	Mean %	Criterion mean	Decision
Sex-for-grade lowers students' self-esteem	310	4.29	.97	86		Accepted
Sex-for-grade occurrence is very rare in higher institutions	310	3.55	1.32	71		Accepted
The dressing manner of students contributes to sex-for-grade occurrence on in higher institutions	310	4.16	.91	83		Accepted
Students who never pay attention are vulnerable to sex-for-grade	310	3.87	.99	77	3.0	Accepted
Students who are truants are susceptible to sex-for-grade act.	310	3.74	.88	75		Accepted
Grand mean/std	310	3.02	1.01	78		Accepted

Table 3 shows respondents' perception towards sex-for-grade in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. Results shows that sex-for-grade lowers students' self-esteem was 4.29 ± 0.97 mean and standard deviation with 86% level of perception, sex-for-grade is rare in higher institutions was 3.55 ± 1.32 with 71% level of perception, indecent dressing can stimulate sex-for-grade was 4.16 ± 0.91 with 83% level of perception, seeking for sex-for-grade due to poor attention to lecturers 3.87 ± 0.99 with 77% level of perception while students' who do not attend classes regularly are susceptible to seeking undue help was 3.74 ± 0.88 with 75% level of perception. Each variables tested showed that students have high level of perception towards sex-for-grade. This was evidenced of the grand mean of 3.92 ± 1.01 with 78% level of perception.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perceptions towards sex-for-grade in BYCOHTECH.

Table 4: Summary of Independent t-test statistics

Independent pairs	N	Mean	STD	DF	T	P value	Confidence interval	Decision
Male	96	40.52	5.08	308	.67	.50	-1.35-2.73	H ₀ accepted
Female	214	39.83	4.59					

Table 4 shows that male has 96 respondents, 40.52 ± 5.08 mean and standard deviation while female with 214 number of respondents has 39.83 ± 4.59 mean and standard deviation. It can be observed from table 5 that for df of 308, P value of .50, t-ratio of .67, and lower and upper confidence level of -1.35 and 2.73 respectively at 95% certainty. Therefore, P value of .50 for a 2-tailed test is greater than the chosen alpha of .05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female students' attitudes and perception towards sex-for-grade was not rejected, that is, it was accepted. This implies that male and female have similar predisposition towards sex-for-grade occurrences in higher institutions in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This current study observed that majority of the participants (49%) had experienced one form of sex-for-grade to another. The level of agreement to the extent in which different forms of sex-for-grade occurred was so revealing that physical sexual harassment was high as 73%, verbal sexual harassment was as high as 76%, non-verbal sexual harassment was 68% which was low, and quid pro quo sexual harassment was as high as 74%. The study observed that the population of the study had experienced high occurrences of sex-for-grade in the institution. Abdussalam (2020) supported these findings that sex-for-grades occurred in several dimensions in universities especially in the federal universities however this study was conducted in a State higher institution. It can therefore be deduced that the occurrence of sex-for-grade is not limited to federal universities alone because the study has revealed that Bayelsa State College of Health Technology being a state institution had been observed high rate of sex-for-grade occurrences in different dimensions because students in the College see sex-for-grade as part of academic fun as well as not as a crime. In a situation as such sex-for-grade will be used deliberately by female students to have academic rewards. This has been established in (Oweifabo & Queensoap, 2024) stating that there are student-centered factors that enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria namely drug influence, deliberate use of sex by some female students as weapon for academic reward, indecent dressing, fun, etc.

Again, the study discovered that students have a high predisposition to sex-for-grade. It was observed that students' attitude towards sex-for-grade was not positive but have no option to resist because they are seen as endangered species.

Nonetheless, this study observed that respondents accepted sex-for-grade as part of fun. They also agreed that it should not be encouraged as well as not to be seen as a crime, indicating that their disposition to sex-for-grade is a two-way dimension. Meanwhile, in the study of Omonigho (2019), sex-for-grade was adjudged as a corrupt practice thus this finding was inconsistent with the previous findings.

The perception level of students on sex-for-grade is high regards to results of this study. Students perceived that sex-for-grade is rare in higher institution. This finding negates the findings of Abdussalam (2020) and Omonigho (2019) whose works revealed that sex-for-grade is common in higher institutions. It implies that students may know what happens in their institution and not in other institution. This is critical to note that this study identified that 49% of the students attested to the occurrence of sex-for-grade however responded with a mean percentage of 71, perceiving that sex-for-grade is rare in higher institution hence what respondents perceived within their institution is different from how they perceived the same subject in another institution.

Another finding of this study that was in line with the findings of Abdussalam (2020) was that the way and manner females dress on campus can stimulate sex-for-grade as well as students who does not attend to classes regularly are susceptible to seeking undue help. These attitudes of students were very high. This study observed that there was no gender difference of students' attitudes and perception toward sex-for-grade Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. This denotes that there is no significant difference between male and female attitudes and perceptions toward sex-for-grade. It implied therefore that both male and female have the similar disposition toward sex-for-grade occurrences in Bayelsa State College of Health Technology, Otuogidi. Ayinla and Adesola (2020) acknowledged that sexual scandals as a public relations nightmare in higher institutions are viewed as a single perception of stakeholders which supports the findings of this current study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings discussed, the study concludes that sex-for-grade occurrence in higher institutions in Bayelsa State was rampant. It was generalized that students have both positive and negative attitude towards sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Bayelsa State, implying a non-directional attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade. The study concluded that both male and female students showed similar attitude and perception towards sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Following the conclusion of the study, the researchers recommend that:

1. The National Assembly and State Assemblies with the management of tertiary institutions should legislate laws that aimed at reducing or eliminating the high occurrences of sex-for-grade in higher institutions.
2. Government through the Ministry of Education, Accreditation Boards/Councils/Commissions and the Tertiary Institutions to ensure the provision of effective counselling centers in all tertiary institutions in Nigeria. This would help engage students to work on their attitudes toward sex-for-grade
3. Non-Governmental Organizations should initiate and carry out advocacy campaign, sensitization and enlightenment in collaboration with tertiary institutions at the beginning of an academic session on the ills of sex-for-grade.

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